

ISic0796

I.Sicily inscription 0796

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Netum

Place of origin (modern)

near Noto

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἐνθάδε κίτε μακαρία[ς]
2. μνήμης Καλλιτύχη· ἔζη
3. σεν ἔτη / πη· ἐτελεύτ[η]
4. [σ]εν δὲ τῆ πρὸ ιε καλα[ν]
5. [δ]ῶν Φεβρουαρίων ἡμέ
6. [ρ]α Σαββάτω /

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493916

EDCS 41400011

EDCS 41300092

PHI 175709

PHI 330111

PHI 331999

Bibliography

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Griesheimer, M. 1989. Quelques inscriptions chrétiennes de Sicile orientale. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana.* 65: 143-177. At 175 no.15

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